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IMPACT OF UNION BUDGET ON INDIAN STOCK MARKET: BSE 100

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ABSTRACT

The Union Budget is perhaps the most watched event in economic policy making in India. The core fiscal issues – taxation, expenditures, fiscal deficit are obviously important for macroeconomics. In addition, governments have often chosen to use the Budget speech as a mechanism for announcing important new policy initiatives, and for outlining some plans for economic policy in the coming months. The Union budget creates enormous market volatility and turnover in the stock market prior to budget as different expectations prevails with respect to taxes impact on individuals, companies and overall economy. After the budget announcement also, volatility continues as Market movers such as FIIS, DIIS, Mutual Funds, Retail Investors, and others adjust their portfolios as per the budget impacts. An empirical research is immensely useful to guide hedging and trading around the Budget date for certain extent. This research has become even more important, pertaining to the fact that stock index derivatives now traded in India. The study considered the stock market behavior on pre and post announcements of Govt. budgets (India: Union Budget) covering the period of study 2003-13. This paper explores the impact of budget on stock market returns and analyses how returns vary with it.

The main aim is to help investor. So that they gain knowledge about returns present in different months, thereby they can invest cautiously. Thus, this study helps the investors to minimize their overall risk and maximize the return of their investment over any period.

KEY WORDS: BSE 100, Investor, Return, Stock Market, Union Budget

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is essential for improving the quality of life. Standard classical and neo-classical theories emphasize the role of investment in enhancing economic growth. Monetary and financial sectors play a key role in mobilizing resources. Financial stability is crucial for promoting investment. In a situation of financial stability, financial institutions and markets are able to efficiently mobilize savings, provide liquidity and allocate investment. The growing role of the financial sector in the efficient allocation of resources at appropriate prices could significantly enhance the efficiency with which our economy functions. If financial markets work well, they will direct resources to their most productive uses. Risks will be more accurately priced and will be borne by those who have appetite for absorbing risks. Real economic activity with higher investments, in both quantity as well as quality, would result in growth with macroeconomic stability and fewer financial uncertainties. A stable financial system facilitates efficient transmission of monetary policy initiatives.

“Markets are constantly in a state of uncertainty and flux and money is made by discounting the obvious and betting on the unexpected.” - George Soros

The above saying of George Soros illustrates the uncertain and fluctuating condition of stock market. There are so many factors and the different determinants (micro or macro levels) of market, by which the market has its more volatile and most fluctuating trend over the span of its life. In the modern economic environment, the stock market index of a country is to act as the barometer of its economic health. The impact of some events that definitely occurs cannot be envisaged by the stock market with confidence due to their nature. The issues of return and movement has become increasingly important in recent times to the Indian investors, regulators, brokers, policy makers, dealers and researchers with the increase in the FII's investment.

Stock Market movement is the most feared and respected word in the midst of the investors. Analysts are aware of its ability to outsmart the finest of the conclusions. The irregular ups and downs add excitement to the market functioning. Sometimes investors earn and sometimes they lost the opportunity. When the irritability of the market turn out to be too much to tolerate and too difficult to recognize, the investors shift away from the market to look for greener pastures in some other areas like gold and real estates, etc.

Government has numerous policies to execute in the overall mission of performing its role to meet up the objectives of social & economic growth. For implementing these policies, it has to spend huge amount of funds on defense, administration, and development, welfare projects and variety of other assistance operations which are all covered in the Union Budget of India.

Each year the union budgets affect the stock market as it brings in changes in policies and presents how the government is going to spend money in the upcoming years, which might be favorable for some and unfavorable for other sectors. This can potentially lead to market ups and downs in that period. In fact, changes are visible even before the budget day. This might be due to the pre-budget press leaks and expectations that already existed into the stocks.

The Budget impacts the economy, the interest rate and the stock markets. In **India**, Union budget is presented in the month of February. All throughout February, the budget distresses shake the Indian stock market, and present the picture of more-or-less much volatility. In this study, We concentrate on BSE 100 Index . Effect is analyzing during the period 2003-2013 particularly pre and post effect on stock market by using Event study methodology. The study of stock market volatility in the Indian stock market (BSE 100) in relation to the event like budget announcement is important for several reasons.

Firstly, movement in stock prices is synonymous with risk and therefore increase in risk associated with a given economic activity should therefore see a reduced level of participation in that activity. In other words, when the Indian stock market exhibits high volatility then a reduced level of participation can be expected and can lead to adverse consequences for investment in the local stock market.

Secondly, changes in stock market volatility, basically can affected the consumption pattern, corporate investment decision, leverage decisions, the business cycle and macroeconomic variable of that country .Therefore, it is important to understand the market behavior by looking at its volatility and as such any implication to the economic can be measured at an early stage.

This study is focus on the impact of the budget announcements on the stock market volatility thus; the sample selected for this study is the **BSE 100 MARKET INDEX**. The events dates for the budget announcement are for 10 years from 2003 until 2013. The data selected is the closing price of the stocks three month before and three month after the budget date.

This study will help investors to analyze the stock prices movement during budget period as well as for various sectors to judge their stock returns how it would affect by govt. fiscal and monetary policies i.e. Union Budget.

Keeping in view the specific objective of the study, the reviews of earlier studies have been shown below: **Pranav Saraswat (2012)** and **Gupta & Kundu(2006)** examined the impact of union budgets on the stock market in terms of volatility of market. **Gurcharan Singh & Salony Kansal (2010)** examined the impact of Budget on stock market by taking S & P CNX Nifty for the study period 1996 to 2009, segregated in to short term, medium term and long term periods. The results suggested that the budget have maximum impact on market trend in short term. They used paired t-test and F-test to compare the average return and variance in return respectively over different period around the budget. They found that with regard to the return an investor has the chance to earn super-profits by investing during the short-term and medium-term periods around the budget. They also concluded that the volatility does not increase in the post budget situation as the time period increases. **Upadhyay Saroj (2006)**, examined that Foreign Institutional Investors (FIT) participation in the Indian Stock Market triggers its upward movements, but at the same time, increased liquidity through FIT investment inflow increases volatility too. **Porwal and Gupta (2005)** explained the hot issue of volatility in the Indian stock markets. The study is based on daily prices of S&P CNX Nifty for the period of 10 years .They found that the year1996 was the most volatile year in the past 10 years; this was due to the political instability and absence of proper regulation. **Verma and Agarwal (2005)** explained the deal with an event study- using budget as an event window for 4 years. It compares the returns on CNX nifty index prior to and subsequent to the budget to assess the impact of the event. The findings of the study indicate that the event have a significant impact on the stock market .**Mohanty (2004)** examined the stock prices reaction to announcement of various policies. Results reflected that stock usually reacted towards the public news quickly. **Thomas and Ajay (2002)** explore the interplay between the Union budget and the stock market. They examined the extent to which the stock market response to the Union Budget. The results of their study found that the stock market appears to be fairly efficient at information processing about the Union Budget. **Rao (1997)** studied the impact of some macroeconomic events including budgets and credit policy of Government as they can increase the volatility of stock prices of market portfolios. **Brown and Warner (1980, 1985)** used monthly returns as well as daily returns to conduct event studies and they concluded that daily data have greater power to signal an event effect when the event date is known. From the literature, its clear that an understanding of stock market volatility over a period of time is important from the point of view of individual investors. Based on these aspects, the study has the following objectives:

- To gather empirical evidence to shed some light on questions directly related to trading and portfolio formation on Indian Stock Exchanges.
- To examine the impact of union budget on the stock market in terms of volatility from 2003-2013 and to compare the daily average stock returns of long run, medium run and short run days before and after the event.
- To examine the returns of BSE 100 from 2003 to 2013.

The study has following limitations:

- The study focused essentially on the share price movement in relation to the public announcement of earnings. The study did not separate 'good' from 'bad' earnings announcements. As a result, the bad announcements seem to have outweighed all the good announcements. Again, there are a number of outliers, and it is known that these have a serious impact on the mean which will impact on the research results.
- It's absolutely depending on secondary information from various websites and databases, so 100% accuracy of the findings, analysis and conclusions might not be attained with my study.
- There is a time constraint as budget topic is quite vast and it intertwines miscellaneous things which are interrelated so I might miss out on factors which are indirectly affecting other factors.
- There is an absence of primary data and very few research and journal papers are available online that throw light upon the relationship between union budget and stock market.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The study has used BSE 100 as a proxy for the stock market because it is the important representative of the Indian Stock Market and also it accounts for one thirds of the turnover. The period covered under the study starts from 2003 to 2013. This period includes total of 11 budgets being presented by various Finance Ministers in the Parliament (shown in Appendix I). A total of 60 trading days before and after the budget has been considered to study the impact of budget. The list of 60 days period in each year is referred in appendix II. This has been done on an assumption, that an impact of budget on share price can be identified on its own for a maximum of 30 days beyond which many other causes may distort the said effect. The study considers only trading days and leaves out any holiday or other days when the market remains closed. These trading days has been segregated into Short-term (3 trading days), Medium-term (15 trading days) and long-term periods (30 trading days) both before and after the budget.

The study is based mainly on secondary data which have been collected from BSE website. The closing prices of BSE 100 has been collected from the official website of BSE. While the budget dates and the name of their respective presenters have been gathered from website of finance ministry (refer to Appendix I).

Hypothesis

Various hypotheses tests have been conducted to understand the statistical significance of the impact. The test tried to compare the average returns during various time periods with one another and also the budget day impact with average return from previous periods. Paired t-test has been used to know the level of significance.

In the hypotheses tests, $\mu(RX1)$, $\mu(RX2)$ and $\mu(RX3)$ represent the average daily returns during the previous 30, 15, 3, trading days. $\mu(RY1)$, $\mu(RY2)$ and $\mu(RY3)$ represent the average daily returns during the next 3, 15, 30 trading days. RZ represent the budget day (event day-end) return.

The null hypotheses

Ho: The budget has no impact on return of BSE 100.

H1: Budget has significant impact on return of BSE 100.

At 5% level of significance hypothesis is tested.

Alternative hypothesis H1 intends to prove that budget day return (i.e. RZ) is more than during the previous 30,15,3 trading days(i.e. $\mu(RX1)$, $\mu(RX2)$ and $\mu(RX3)$) for all budgets. In the next tests, alternative hypothesis H1 intends to prove that post budget average return i.e. (next 3,15,30 trading days (i.e $\mu(RY1)$, $\mu(RY2)$ and $\mu(RY3)$) are more than pre- budget average return i.e. (previous 30,15,3 trading days(i.e., $\mu(RX1)$, $\mu(RX2)$ and $\mu(RX3)$) for all budgets.

In next part of the study, the variance of returns (σ^2) have been compared between various time periods in order to find out the extent of movement (σ) in the market around the budget period. Two sets of hypothesis tests conducted in this part of analysis.

- In the first set, variances of return during the short-term, medium term and long term periods in the post budget situation have been compared to one another, i.e., variances of returns between Y1 & Y2, Y2 & Y3 and Y1 & Y3 respectively have been examined into where

Y1: post short period (3 days)

Y2: post medium period (15 days)

Y3: post long period (30 days).

These comparisons have been made because variances are expected to rise with the increasing time period and fluctuations in return is also historically found to be continuing in a post-budget situation.

The null hypothesis

H0 in tests assumes no change in variance i.e., the variances are equal.

$$\sigma^2(Y1) = \sigma^2(Y2) = \sigma^2(Y3)$$

The alternative hypothesis: H1 is that variance during Y2 is more than that of during Y1, variance during Y3 is more than that of during Y2 and variance during Y3 is more than that of during Y1 respectively.

- In second set, each of the post- budget short -term, medium-term and long-term periods has been compared to the long-term pre- budget period, i.e. variances of returns between X1 & Y1(pre short period & post shot period), X1& Y2(pre short period& post medium period) and X1 & Y3(pre short period& post long period) respectively have been examined into. These tests have been framed with a more empirically established fact that the variances in returns after budget for different periods are expected to be greater than the pre-budget long term variance.

F-test applied for testing the significance level.

FINDINGS

Table I depicts the daily average returns and budget day returns presented by BSE 100 during the previous and next 3, 15, 30 days around the budget day.

Budget day effect on BSE 100:

The first set of paired t-tests measure the on-day (Z) influence of budget on BSE 100 when compared to the previous 3, 15 and 30 days. A cursory glance at the **Table 1** highlights that in most of the cases budget day returns are more than the returns during the previous 30,15,3 trading days. Therefore, when the budget day returns (Z) compared with the long term pre- budget return, it shows that budget day returns exceed (9 out of 11 budgets),when the budget day returns (Z) compared with the medium term pre-budget return, it shows that budget day returns exceed (6 out of 11 budgets) and when the budget day returns (Z) compared with the short term pre-budget return, it shows that budget day returns exceed (6 out of 11 budgets).

Table 1: Daily Average Return In BSE 100

Year	X1 (last 30 days)	X2 (last 15 days)	X3(last 3 days)	Z (budget day)	Y1(next 3 days)	Y2 (next 15 days)	Y3(next 30 days)
2003	75.28	77.17	76.3	75.04	74.29	76.99	74.9
2004	85.79	86.09	11.57	79.52	87.25	92.13	89.51
2005	17.74	17.98	-79.11	23.52	19.95	22.06	22.47
2006	48.89	49.78	76.87	50.13	53.4	52.4	56.22
2007	35.5	31.81	-36.09	20.36	18.1	14.56	14.32
2008	32.16	34.55	8.62	45.71	37.53	34.64	30.36
2009	-50.48	-50.48	-246.1	-52.51	-52.65	-50.1	-46.02
2010	84.38	85.03	-268.43	93.92	111.28	110.5	101.73
2011	8.88	8.76	-8.68	5.71	6.41	5.15	3.95
2012	-1.24	0.34	-96.12	0.44	-3.15	-3.03	-3.7
2013	-37.23	-37.6	-11.51	-38.49	-38.34	-36.65	-36.98

Source: Calculated from the data taken from BSE website for said period.

Note: All returns are in percentage

T- values from Paired t-Test

Table 2 :Effect of Budget day Returns on BSE 100

	X1 and Z	X2 and Z	X3 and Z
Actual value(5%)	0.88	0.99	2.04*
Table value(5%)	1.76	1.76	1.76

Source: Calculated from the data based on Table 1

Note: * Signifies that Null Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected.

The above findings (Table I) have been further statistically tested by Paired t test (Table II). The budgets are found to take the markets by surprise that market has greatly influence just before the event i.e. relation between X3 and Z(2.04> 1.76) which indicates Alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: Impact of Budgets on BSE 100 stock index

Periods	Short term period			Medium term period			Long term period		
	x1 and y1	x2 and y1	x3 and y1	x1 and y2	x2 and y2	x3 and y2	x1 and y3	x2 and y3	x3 and y3
actual value (5%)	2.68*	1.85*	0.05	1.81*	0.66	0.05	0.83	0.91	0.02
Table value (5%)	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76	1.76

Source: Calculated from the data based on Table I

Note: * Signifies that Null Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected (actual value >table value)

Table III provides the second set of tests, which prove that budget have maximum impact in the short term(alternative hypothesis have been accepted in two cases).In medium term, the alternative hypothesis have been accepted in one out of three cases and in long term, no alternative hypothesis have been

accepted. In total, the actual values exceed the tabular values in four cases (2+1+0) out of nine at the right tail. i.e.

In Short period: X1 & Y1(2.68>1.76), X2 & Y1(1.85>1.76)

In Medium period: X1 & Y2(1.81>1.76)

In long period : Zero

This proves that budgets, when taken together, have the maximum impact in the short term post-budget period, with some impact extending into the medium-term and no significant impact at all on long- term average returns.

Table 4: Variance of return in BSE 100

Year	X1 (last 30 days)	X2 (last 15 days)	X3(last 3 days)	Y1(next 3 days)	Y2 (next 15 days)	Y3(next 30 days)
2003	0.56	0.65	0.33	0.19	0.33	0.85
2004	2.98	2.58	1.29	0.02	0.21	0.73
2005	0.84	0.53	0.03	0.38	0.48	0.74
2006	0.54	0.38	0.12	0.11	0.82	0.61
2007	2.1	2.66	0.28	2.98	4.68	3.5
2008	4.8	3.49	0.3	1.53	9.13	10.5
2009	3.08	2.34	0.11	1.05	4.47	5.24
2010	1.15	0.51	0.52	0.64	0.54	0.41
2011	1.99	1.39	0.03	0.04	0.83	1.03
2012	1.69	2.19	0.87	0.18	1.13	1.56
2013	0.48	0.85	0.07	0.76	0.72	0.74

Source: Calculated from the data taken from BSE website for said period

Table 5: F-Test comparing Variance among the returns (Post budget) with one another

Year	actual value	Table value(5%)	actual value	Table value(5%)	actual value	Table value (5%)
	Y1 and Y2	df=14/2	Y2 and Y3	df=29/14	Y3 and Y1	df=29/2
2003	1.73	19.42	2.58	2.31	4.47	3.33
2004	10.5	19.42	3.48	2.31	36.5	3.33
2005	1.26	19.42	1.54	2.31	1.95	3.33
2006	7.45	19.42	1.34	2.05	5.55	3.33
2007	1.57	19.42	1.34	2.05	1.17	3.33
2008	5.96	19.42	1.15	2.31	6.86	3.33
2009	4.25	19.42	1.17	2.31	4.99	3.33
2010	1.18	3.74	1.32	2.05	1.56	19.46
2011	20.75*	19.42	1.24	2.31	25.75	3.33
2012	6.27	19.42	1.38	2.31	8.67	3.33
2013	1.05	3.74	1.03	2.31	1.03	19.46

Source: Calculated from the data based on Table IV

Note: * actual value > table value

Table V shows F-test values for the tests that compare the variance (given in Table IV) among the returns in BSE 100 during short- term, medium-term, and long-term periods after the budget with one another. In only one case we find the actual value exceeded the tabular value .This signifies that movement does generally reflect in post budget situation when we relate short and medium term post budget period.

Table 6: F-test comparing variance among the returns during Post-Budget Periods with Long term Pre-Budget Period

year	Actual value	Table value (5%)	actual value	Table value (5%)	Actual value	Table value (5%)
	X1 and Y1	df=29/2	X1 and Y2	df=29/14	X1 and Y3	df=29/29
2003	2.95	19.46	1.70	2.31	1.52	1.84
2004	14.90	19.46	14.19*	2.31	4.08*	1.85
2005	2.21	19.46	1.75	2.31	1.14	1.85
2006	4.91	19.46	1.52	2.05	1.13	1.84
2007	1.42	3.33	2.23*	2.05	1.67	1.84
2008	3.14	19.46	1.90	2.05	2.19*	1.84
2009	2.93	19.46	1.45	2.31	1.70	1.84
2010	1.80	19.46	2.13	2.31	2.80*	1.85
2011	49.75*	19.46	2.40*	2.31	1.93*	1.85
2012	9.39	19.46	1.50	2.31	1.08	1.85
2013	1.58	3.33	1.50	2.05	1.54	1.84

Source: Calculated from the data based on Table IV

Note: * Signifies that Null Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected

Table VI depicts specifically F-test values for the tests that compare the variance of returns in BSE 100 during short-term, medium-term, and long-term post budget periods with that of long-term pre-budget period. The long term period shows the maximum number of significant cases (in 4 out of 11 budgets) as compared to medium term (in 3 out of 11 budgets) and short-term (in 1 out of 11 budgets). It indicates that the long term period after the budget tend to be more effective than the medium-term and the short-term periods when compared to similar long-term before the budget.

The test values, however, do not prove whether the market index will rise or fall in the post budget period because they have arisen from changes in the value of index after the presentation of budget. The increase in the tax on dividend outgo for companies and subjecting export earnings to a 20 per cent tax per annum over the next five years were seen as unfavorable by the market and also, the budget failed to address macro-economic issues such as fiscal deficit, government spending and public sector disinvestment. In 2003 once again the stock markets fell by 4 per cent with a lukewarm budget. In 2007 stock market crashed by near about 4 per cent. This was the biggest fall on a Budget day in the past five years. The fall was due to market unfriendly union budget which includes increased dividend distribution tax from 12.5 per cent to 15 per cent, increase in excise duty on cement prices and followed by the extension of minimum alternate tax (MAT) for the IT sector.

CONCLUSION

The Government Budget announcement is one of the important factors as it is related to the financial or economic health of country involving all the industries. The study reveals that in India, the union budget mainly affects the stock market in short term mainly and medium term also. But in long term those budgets have not any significant impact on stock market trend as investors are adjusted with the announcements.

When the Finance Minister reads out the budget speech, the efficient stock market should react within seconds to each sentence that is read out, in terms of a direct impact on stock prices of firms and industries that are either positively or negatively affected. Given that intra-day stock price information is

now available, it should be possible to test whether such impacts do take place, and whether there is overreaction or under-reaction in these immediate responses.

The Indian economy has seen major changes in the role of Government, and hence the Union Budget, in the economy from 1991 onwards. The stock market has seen major improvements in liquidity from 1995 onwards. The technologies and institutional mechanisms for transferring and processing information, which are the foundation of information processing by financial markets, have been transformed over the years.

Hence, the empirical evidence shown here – based on the average behavior surrounding 11 Budgets from 2003-2013 is of limited value in making statements about the relationship between the stock market and the Union Budget *today*. As further data accumulates, it would be important to reassess the evidence by focusing on a homogeneous policy regime, i.e. the period from 1995 onwards.

With regard to return an investor has the chance to earn super-profits by investing during the short-term and medium-term periods around the budget (upto 15 trading days). However, he also faces the risk of abnormal losses if his expectations are not met from the budget. This is also true in case of trading on the budget day. As one moves away from the budget day (up to 30 trading days), the paired t-tests do not show any significant change in average returns. Hence budgets are seen to have effect only up to 15 trading days from the budget day so far as return is concerned. Stock market index, on the other hand, does not generally increase in post budget situation as the time period increases. But the long term period after the budget tends to be more volatile than the medium-term and the short-term periods when compared to similar long-term period before the budget.

Our results may be summarized as follows:

- The stock market appears to be fairly efficient at information processing about the Union Budget.
- Union Budgets add 10% to the stock index, on average, and yield elevated volatility starting from the Budget date for the following 30 trading days or so.
- There is a puzzle in the post-budget period, where equity investors are exposed to substantially higher risk without higher returns as a consequence. It immediately suggests hedging strategies for equity investors, who could benefit by short-selling index futures on or near budget date. In the long term, if enough economic agent engage in such behavior, we may see a shift in the behavior of the index.
- The values of co-efficient of variation and standard deviation pertaining to the market capitalization is slightly less volatile in BSE.
- High turnover of BSE may be due to its transparency, technological sophistication, and due to the efficient payment and settlement framework.

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APPENDIX 1: List of Budgets Covered

S.NO.	DATE OF BUDGET ANNOUNCEMENT	PRESENTORS (FINANCE MINISTERS)
1	28-Feb-03	Jaswant Singh's Budget
2	8-Jul-04	P.Chidambaram's Budget
3	28-Feb-05	P.Chidambaram's Budget
4	28-Feb-06	P.Chidambaram's Budget
5	28-Feb-07	P.Chidambaram's Budget
6	29-Feb-08	P.Chidambaram's Budget
7	6-Jul-09	P.Chidambaram's Budget
8	28-Feb-10	Pranab Mukherjee's Budget
9	28-Feb-11	Pranab Mukherjee's Budget
10	29-Feb-12	Pranab Mukherjee's Budget
11	28-Feb-13	P.Chidambaram's Budget

APPENDIX II : Period Covered for Each Budget

NO.	S.	YEAR	Period(60 Trading Days Plus Budget Day)
1		2003	16/1/03 to 15/4/03
2		2004	27/5/04 to 19/8/04
3		2005	13/1/05 to 12/4/05
4		2006	12/1/06 to 12/4/06
5		2007	13/1/07 to 12/4/07
6		2008	12/1/08 to 12/4/08
7		2009	25/5/09 to 17/8/09
8		2010	13/1/10 to 12/4/10
9		2011	13/1/11 to 12/4/11
10		2012	13/1/12 to 12/4/12
11		2013	13/1/13 to 12/4/13